

Fully Integrated Multi-layer Stacked Structure of Integrated Inductor with Patterned Ground Shield

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Abstract—In this work, we propose fully integrated multi-layer stacked topology of asymmetrical inductor with patterned ground shield (PGS), which also serves as capacitor. The main aim of the study is efficient usage of limited chip area for integrated passive components by challenging layout properties of asymmetrical integrated inductor and integrated MOS capacitor and enhancing their main electrical properties. Several principles of geometry modifications (vertical and horizontal parallelization, slicing, tapering, equal path lengths) were applied to a four-turn octagonal asymmetrical integrated inductor with the series DC resistance $R_L = 1.75 \Omega$ and inductance $L = 11.66 \text{ nH}$ on low frequencies. Remaining area under integrated inductor was used for a capacitor with capacitance $C_{PGS} = 1.6 \text{ nF}$ and the equivalent series resistance $R_C = 7.25 \Omega$. The whole structure was designed in a standard 65nm CMOS technology for use in a switched DC-DC power converter working in MHz-range for a Photovoltaic (PV) Energy Harvester (EH).

Index Terms—Integrated Inductor, Integrated Capacitor, MLS, Slicing, Tapering, EPL, PGS

I. INTRODUCTION

Requirements on electrical devices are continuously rising. With an emphasis on price and power consumption of electronic circuits, scaling of the technology is still relevant parameter that is pushed into its limits. Moore's law has been present in the circuit design for decades. However, apart from transistors, other passive components should be managed as well. Fully integrated passive components widely used in analog design (e.g. power management, signal conversion, filtering, etc.) need to have increased power density.

Lack of high-quality and area-efficient fully integrated passive components is present in low-cost technologies. As the technology processes continues to develop, new methods of circuit design have to be challenged. Thus, in our work, we emphasize high area-efficient design of passive components also in a standard all-purpose CMOS technologies. The structure proposed in this paper is a combination of on-chip inductor and capacitor in a multi-layer stacked structure, which

is intended to be used in a fully integrated DC-DC boost converter.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses advanced layout techniques used for enhancing electrical properties of integrated inductors – multi-layer stacked (MLS) topology, slicing, tapering, equal path lengths (EPL) and patterned ground shield (PGS). Section III describes an integrated capacitor implemented into the proposed PGS structure. These two sections also presents the results obtained by simulations in the High Frequency Electromagnetic Simulation Software (HFSS) and Q3D Extractor in ANSYS Electronics Desktop and CADENCE Virtuoso for both integrated devices - inductor and capacitor. Alternative schematics for the whole structure is described in Section IV. Section V summarizes main properties of the proposed fully integrated MLS structure of integrated inductor with PGS and an integrated capacitor; and suggests its application.

II. INTEGRATED INDUCTOR

Spiral inductors are one of the most challenging components to fully integrate on a chip. Several loss mechanisms restrict the achievable quality factor Q , while area constraints limit the inductance L value. Low cost technologies does not support usage of multiple thick (T) or ultra-thick (UT) metal layers to reduce series resistance R_L of structures. Another approaches must then be chosen to enhance electrical properties of such structures. Few geometry modifications were chosen for our object and are reviewed as follows:

A. Multi-Layer Stacked Topology

Principle of multi-layer stacked inductor topology is vertical parallelization of metal layers. This can be utilized as multiple turns located above each other connected in series or parallel connection of two or more identical turns. While the series connection increases the length of inductor that also increases

inductance L and series resistance R_L , the parallel connection maintains inductance L unchanged but increases quality factor Q by decreasing series resistance R_L of the integrated inductor.

In our research, both connections were investigated. By series connection of four turns in aluminium redistributive (RDL) layer and UT copper layer (two turns in each layer), we created a 4-turn inductor. Parallel connection was then used for outer bottom turn in UT metal layer. Outer bottom turn was copied to T metal layer underneath to reduce its series resistance R_L . Series resistance R_L of this turn increases because of metal paths slotting in UT layer of the inductor to comply with the maximum metal density in design rules. Detail of slots in UT metal and parallelization in T metal layer is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Detail of slots in outer turn in UT metal and parallelization in T metal

B. Slicing

Horizontal parallelization of metal paths in one metal layer is called slicing. Parallel connection of multiple metal paths (slices) increases turn width while complying with the maximum allowed metal width. By splitting one metal path into more slices, surface of each turn is enlarged that effectively suppresses series resistance R_L caused by eddy currents [1].

In our structure, the number of parallel metal paths in each turn was 8. This number was determined to comply with design rules (maximum and minimum width), skin depth at frequency of interest (1 – 100 MHz) and available area.

C. Tapering

Tapering is geometry modification based on varying width of metal paths [2] with respect to generated magnetic field around the integrated inductor. Time-varying magnetic field induces eddy currents back into the structure and causes inhomogeneity of current density in each metal path. Eddy currents tend to have the most considerable impact on series resistance R_L in the core of the inductor, where the induction of magnetic field is the strongest. This fact causes that the outer side of the inside metal paths contributes to current conduction the least, and therefore, width of this path can be reduced. This effect increases with the frequency increase.

To maintain the series resistance R_L for DC component of inductor current I_L , the reduced path width from inner paths should be added to outer metal paths. Change of path widths of each metal path should be close to linear [3]. In our structure, limits of the narrowest and widest metal paths were chosen as the maximum and minimum allowed limits by technology design rules, respectively.

Countering the magnitude of eddy currents also improves the inductor quality factor Q by decreasing their own magnetic field that has the opposite direction to the original magnetic field of the integrated inductor. This effect is suppressed in a positive manner by both slicing and tapering techniques.

D. Equal Path Length

Equal path length (EPL) is technique that also counters the effect of inhomogeneity of current distribution in the inductor structure [4], [5] and is closely related to use of slicing technique. When one inductor turn is divided into more metal paths connected in parallel, the inhomogeneity of current density is present because of increasing distance of paths from the core of inductor. To maintain relatively equal impact of time-varying magnetic field on each path, the outer paths of one turn are cross-connected to inner paths of the next turn in the middle of structure. This connection balances the series resistance of each path of individual inductor turns. Example of EPL crossing for 4 slices is shown in Figure 2. This technique can be extended into any number of slices. Realizing that Figure 2 also shows a cross section of inductor, the series connection of individual turns can be observed here.

The final proposed structure of a fully integrated inductor is 4-turn multi-layer asymmetrical inductor realized using three top metal layers with 2 turns in top RDL metal layer, 2 turns in UT metal layer (from which one turn is also parallelized in T metal layer). Every turn consists of 8 parallel metal slices and EPL crossing is implemented in the middle

Fig. 2: Example of EPL crossing for 4 slices

Fig. 3: Proposed MLS integrated inductor

of inductor between *Port1* and *Port2* three times. Tapering technique was implemented as well. The proposed structure of integrated inductor, shown in Figure 3, has dimensions $560.65 \mu\text{m} \times 881.65 \mu\text{m}$, and thus covering approximate area $A_L = 0.494 \text{ mm}^2$.

E. Patterned Ground Shield

Patterned ground shield (PGS) is a metal structure implemented in metal layer between the integrated inductor and substrate to suppress energy losses caused by coupling between inductor and substrate [6]. Substrate losses stem from the penetration of electric field into the substrate and are frequency dependent [7]. Shape of the shield should be designed with respect to the shape of inductor, especially to the shape of generated magnetic and electric fields. Metal strips that form PGS are perpendicular to the direction of inductor turns and generated fields. Slots that are separating individual metal strips are dividing PGS into smaller sections. In this way, loops of induced currents as well as their magnitudes are reduced. Metal strips should be sufficiently wide and close enough to block the electric field of the inductor from substrate. The metal strips are connected in the middle of PGS to prevent creating a loop for induced current.

The designed structure of PGS covered approximate area $A_C = 0.638 \text{ mm}^2$ ($644.98 \mu\text{m} \times 989.42 \mu\text{m}$) and is shown in Figure 4. Comparison of frequency characteristics for inductors with and without PGS are shown in Figure 5. Significant results of the performed comparison are also summarized in

Fig. 4: Proposed structure of PGS without MOS-based capacitors

TABLE I: Main parameters of MLS inductor with and without PGS

Excitation		1 → 2		
Parameter		w/o PGS	w PGS	Variation
L_{max}	[nH]	42.5	44.9	+5.65 %
$F @ L_{max}$	[GHz]	1.00	0.71	-29 %
$L_{f \rightarrow 0}$	[nH]	11.61	11.66	+0.43 %
R_{DC}	[Ω]	1.77	1.75	-1.13 %
Q_{max}	[-]	10.85	8.39	-22.67 %
$F @ Q_{max}$	[MHz]	408.35	325.13	-20.38 %
F_{SR}	[GHz]	1.09	0.76	-30.28 %

Excitation		2 → 1		
Parameter		w/o PGS	w PGS	Variation
L_{max}	[nH]	49.8	59	+18.47 %
$F @ L_{max}$	[GHz]	1.03	0.86	-16.51 %
$L_{f \rightarrow 0}$	[nH]	11.61	11.66	+0.43 %
R_{DC}	[Ω]	1.77	1.75	-1.13 %
Q_{max}	[-]	11.48	10.09	-12.1 %
$F @ Q_{max}$	[MHz]	437.55	409.32	-6.45 %
F_{SR}	[GHz]	1.09	0.92	-15.59 %

Table I. Adding the PGS under inductor caused changes in frequency characteristics, particularly by increasing parasitic capacitance between inductor and GND potential (substrate or PGS structure). This capacitance is unevenly distributed between *Port1* and *Port2*, thus a drift of curves for different direction of excitation. An increase in capacitance C_{g1} of *Port1* is observed due to the fact that it is connected to the bottom turn in UT and T metal layers while the *Port2* is connected to the top turn in RDL layer. Therefore, *Port1* should be connected to a PV cell with non-pulsating DC voltage, while *Port2* with lower parasitic capacitance C_{g2} will be connected to the switches of a DC-DC converter. One can also observe a drift in peaks of inductance L (Figure 5(a)) and quality factor Q (Figure 5(c)) to lower frequencies. Similar trend is also visible in frequency characteristics of series resistance R_L (Figure 5(b)), what means decrease of self-resonance frequency F_{SR} . The peaks of all curves are more affected by this parasitic capacitance for direction of excitation from *Port1* to *Port2*.

III. INTEGRATED CAPACITOR

The area available under integrated inductor should not be used for other parts of the circuit in general, especially for active parts if not necessary. This could negatively affect electrical properties of not only the inductor but also of other components. However, this area could utilize a capacitor implemented into the PGS structure. With the PGS structure, shifting from the lowest to second lowest metal layer, there is possibility of creating an integrated capacitor using a MOS FET structure underneath. The lowest metal layer is then used for a parallel connection of transistors. The bulk contacts of

(a) Inductance

(b) Series Resistance

(c) Quality Factor

Fig. 5: Comparison of frequency characteristics of inductor with PGS and without PGS

every transistor are shorted with source and drain contacts, and through the lowest metal layer connected to PGS with GND potential. In this paper, GND potential is always meant as the global grounding substrate potential. Gate contacts of transistors are shorted together in the lowest metal layer, creating the second terminal of the capacitor. Routing of connections between transistors was designed to copy the PGS structure. Visualization of connections between metal layers and substrate, as well as their shapes are shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Shape of capacitor and PGS connections (*Poly layer for MOS capacitor is not shown)

For the purpose of integrated capacitor, a native NMOS transistor was used as it represents the best solution in terms of flatband voltage V_{fb} and the maximum capacitance C_{max} (compared to standard NMOS and PMOS transistors). Comparison was performed by simulations in CADENCE Virtuoso using BSIMv4 models of transistors. Native NMOS has the maximum capacitance $C_{max} = 336.24 \text{ fF}$ and the flatband voltage $V_{fb} = 980 \text{ mV}$. Significant value of capacitance is at gate voltage $V_G = 500 \text{ mV}$ that represents the minimum voltage of selected PV cell in the maximum power point V_{mpp} . This value for native NMOS capacitor is $C_{V_G=0.5V} = 313.82 \text{ fF}$. All capacitances are simulated with one MOS transistor connected as capacitor with dimensions of one transistor under the PGS structure. The number of parallel connected capacitors under PGS is 4696, therefore full capacitance of the parallel gate oxide capacitance is $C_{ox} = 1.58 \text{ nF}$. To the total capacitance of PGS, we have to also add a capacitance created between metal strips of the PGS. The final capacitance value obtained from simulations in

Fig. 7: Comparison of C-V characteristics MOS FET capacitors

TABLE II: Significant parameters of MOS FET capacitors

Parameter		NMOS	Native NMOS	PMOS
C_{max}	[fF]	339.19	336.24	318.21
$C @ V_G = 0.5 V$	[fF]	239.51	313.82	168.78
V_{fb}	[V]	1.24	0.98	1.30

Q3D simulator was $C_M = 17.58 pF$. Similarly, the equivalent series resistance R_C of the capacitor under PGS obtained by simulations was $R_C = 7.25 \Omega$. The total capacitance of the integrated capacitor placed under PGS is $C_{PGS} = 1.6 nF$. The significant simulation results are compared in Table II, and C-V characteristics of MOS transistors are shown in Figure 7.

IV. MODEL OF PROPOSED STRUCTURE

For the purpose of using the proposed structure in the future, alternative schematics were derived for both devices – inductor and capacitor. These are shown in Figure 8(a) and Figure 8(b), respectively. Conventional wideband inductor model [8] was supplemented by capacitor C_s that models capacitance between the inductor turns and resistor R_{in} to better fit simulated series resistance of the proposed integrated inductor. Inductor L_s and resistor R_s model inductor behaviour at lower frequencies, while inductor L_p and resistor R_p represent inductor behaviour at high frequencies. K is mutual coupling coefficient of inductors L_s and L_p . Resistors R_{g1} and R_{g2} , and capacitors C_{g1} and C_{g2} model coupling between the inductor and PGS connected to GND potential.

Alternative schematic of a capacitor under the PGS is a parallel connection of simulated capacitance of the gate oxide C_{ox} and capacitance between metal paths C_M with

TABLE III: Values of components in model of integrated inductor and capacitor

Inductor					
L_s	[nH]	11.52	R_{in}	[mΩ]	10
R_s	[Ω]	1.75	L_p	[nH]	1.1
C_s	[pF]	2.15	R_p	[Ω]	87
R_{g1}	[Ω]	17	R_{g2}	[Ω]	22
C_{g1}	[pF]	1.60	C_{g2}	[pF]	0.50
K	[-]	0.8			

Capacitor		
R_C	[Ω]	7.25
C_{ox}	[nF]	1.58
C_M	[pF]	17.58

resistor R_C as equivalent series resistance of the capacitor connected in series. Values of all components in models of the integrated inductor and capacitor are summarized in Table III. Comparison of frequency characteristics of the inductor and its alternative schematic is shown in Figure 9. The greatest and the most significant deviations of frequency characteristics are in the curve peaks. Values of the greatest deviation for inductance, series resistance, and quality factor are 4.08%, 1.27%, and 2.29%, respectively.

V. RESULTS

All results were obtained from simulations in the High Frequency Electromagnetic Simulation Software (HFSS) and Q3D Extractor of ANSYS Electronics Desktop and also in CADENCE Virtuoso. All structures comply with process design rules, and were designed for a standard general-purpose 65nm CMOS technology without any post-process steps. The aim for future use of structure is in a fully integrated switched DC-DC boost voltage converter. The final proposed structure is shown in Figure 10.

Best achieved inductance at lower frequencies of the proposed MLS integrated inductor with PGS is $L_{f \rightarrow 0} = 11.66 nH$ and inductance density is $L_A = 23.59 nH/mm^2$. The value of series DC resistance of the inductor of 1.75Ω was achieved, and quality factor is $Q_{max} = 10.09$ at frequency $f_Q = 409.32 MHz$. Total capacitance of the proposed capacitor integrated into PGS structure is $C = 1.6 nF$ and the capacitance density is $C_A = 2.48 nF/mm^2$. Frequency characteristic of the proposed structure model are fitted with the greatest error from simulated results up to 4.08%.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, several layout techniques for achieving better performance of fully integrated inductors were investigated in means of higher inductance, quality factor and lower series resistance. Electrical parameters were improved to maximize the area efficiency of passive components for a standard general-purpose bulk CMOS technology without a need for

Fig. 8: Model of integrated inductor and capacitor

(a) Inductance

(b) Series Resistance

(c) Quality Factor

Fig. 9: Comparison of frequency characteristics of inductor and its alternative schematic

any special (e.g. RF, SOI, BiCMOS) technologies or post-layout steps (e.g. bondwire [9], silicon-embedded, on-Silicon, suspended [10], etc.). One of the most examined technique was usage of Patterned Ground Shield, which also utilizes an on-chip capacitor formed by parallel connection of native NMOS transistors. Fully integrated multi-layer stacked structure of inductor and capacitor will be implemented as a switched inductor and decoupling input capacitor in a fully integrated switched DC-DC voltage converter for PV energy harvester. Therefore, alternative schematic model of the proposed structure was also derived from simulation results.

Fig. 10: Proposed MLS structure with integrated inductor and capacitor

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